

Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
ACTINEDIDA														
Eriophyidae (Gall Mites)														
<i>Acalitus ferrugineum</i> Farlow & Hagen, 1885)	<i>Fagus grandifolia</i>	Beech	G	x										
<i>Aceria dina</i> (Styer & Keifer, 1978)	<i>Nyssa sylvatica</i>	Tupelo	G			x								44
<i>Aceria fraxiniflora</i> (Felt, 1906)	<i>Fraxinus</i>	Ash	G											Mill Hill park
<i>Aculops rhois</i> (Stebbins, 1909)	<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i> , <i>T. vernix</i>	Poison Ivy, Poison Sumac	G			x							x	23, 31, 32, 35
<i>Eriophyes cerasicrumena</i> (Walsh, 1868)	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry	G	x								x	x	45
<i>Eriophyes emarginatae</i> (Keifer, 1939)	<i>Prunus</i>	Plum	G											9
" <i>Eriophyes coryli</i> " Stebbins, 1909	<i>Corylus</i>	Hazelnut	G										x	
" <i>Eriophyes</i> " sp.	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i>	Arrowwood	G											45
HEMIPTERA														
Adelgidae (Adelgids)														
<i>Adelges abietis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Picea abies</i>	Norway Spruce	G											31
Aphididae (Aphids)														
<i>Hamamelistes spinosus</i> Shimer, 1867	<i>Hamamelis virginiana</i>	Witch Hazel	G											Coskata
<i>Tamalia coweni</i> (Cockerell, 1905)	<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i>	Bearberry	G											10, 24
<i>Tetraneura</i>	<i>Ulmus</i>	Elm	G											town
Liviidae (Liviid Psyllids)														
<i>Livia bifasciata</i> Provancher, 1886	<i>Juncus canadensis</i>	Canada Rush	G						x					
Phylloxeridae (Phylloxerans)														
<i>Phylloxera</i> sp.	<i>Carya tomentosa</i>	Mockernut Hickory	G	x										
<i>Phylloxerina nyssae</i> (Pergande, 1904)	<i>Nyssa sylvatica</i>	Tupelo	G											37
COLEOPTERA														
Buprestidae (Metallic Wood-boring Beetles)														
<i>Brachys aerosus</i> (Melsheimer, 1845)	<i>Castanea mollissima</i> , <i>Corylus americana</i> , <i>C. cornuta</i> , <i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Chinese Chestnut, American Hazelnut, Beaked Hazelnut, Scrub Oak	M, P						x					27, 31, 73
<i>Brachys aeruginosus</i> Gory, 1841	<i>Quercus</i>	Oak	P, S			x								59

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<i>Brachys howdeni</i> Hesperheide, 2016	<i>Epigaea repens</i>	Trailing Arbutus	M, S											29, 31, 36
<i>Brachys ovatus</i> (Weber, 1801)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M, S						x					45, 64
<i>Brachys</i> n. sp.	<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i>	Maleberry	M, S											31, 44
<i>Brachys</i> spp.	<i>Fagus grandifolia</i> , <i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. stellata</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Beech, Scrub Oak, Post Oak, Black Oak	L, M	x	x				x					24, 31, 44, 57, 65
Chrysomelidae (Leaf Beetles)														
<i>Erynephala maritima</i> (LeConte, 1865)	<i>Salicornia</i>	Glasswort	M, S											44
<i>Microrhopala vittata</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	<i>Solidago rugosa</i>	Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	M											32
<i>Sumitrosis inaequalis</i> (Weber, 1801)	<i>Symphotrichum undulatum</i>	Wavy-leaved Aster	M, S			x								31
<i>Oulema palustris</i> (Blatchley, 1913)	<i>Cirsium horridulum</i>	Yellow Thistle	M, S											5, 46
<i>Phyllotreta chalybeipennis</i> (Crotch, 1873)	<i>Cakile edentula</i>	Sea Rocket	M, S											50
Curculionidae (Weevils)														
<i>Isochnus sequensi</i> (Stierlin, 1894)	<i>Populus tremuloides</i> , <i>Salix purpurea</i>	Quaking Aspen, Basket Willow	M, S											54, 56
<i>Orchestes mixtus</i> Blatchley, 1916	<i>Corylus americana</i> , <i>C. cornuta</i>	American Hazelnut, Beaked Hazelnut	M	x		x								27, 44
<i>Orchestes pallicornis</i> Say, 1831	<i>Prunus maritima</i> , <i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry, Beach Plum	M, P	x						x				19, 45, 50
Megalopodidae (Megalopodid Leaf Beetles)														
<i>Zeugophora consanguinea</i> Crotch, 1873	<i>Populus alba</i>	White Poplar	P											73
HYMENOPTERA														
Argidae (Argid Sawflies)														
<i>Schizocerella pilicornis</i> (Holmgren, 1868)	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Purslane	M											23
Bethylidae (Bethylid Wasps)														
<i>Goniozus</i> sp.	<i>Corlyus americana</i> (<i>Phyllonorycter intermixta</i>)	American Hazelnut	M, S											31

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Braconidae (Braconid Wasps)														
<i>Colastes</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Coptotriche citrinipennella</i>)	Scrub Oak	M											24
<i>Gnamptodon</i> sp.	<i>Bolboschoenus robustus</i> (<i>Acalypttris</i>)	Sturdy Bulrush	M, S											44
<i>Oenonogastra</i> sp.	<i>Solidago gigantea</i> (<i>Nemorimyza?</i>)	Late Goldenrod	M											40
<i>Opius</i> sp.	<i>Ilex opaca</i> (<i>Phytomyza illicicola</i>)	American Holly	M											19
<i>Pholetesor</i> sp.	<i>Acer rubrum</i> (<i>Phyllonorycter</i>)	Red Maple	co-coon											31
<i>Pholetesor</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Cameraria quercivorella</i>)	Scrub Oak	M, S											19
<i>Polystenidea</i> sp.	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> (<i>Bucculatrix ivella</i>)	Groundsel	M											25
<i>Pseudognaptodon</i> sp.	<i>Prunus serotina</i> (<i>Stigmella prunifoliella</i>)	Black Cherry	M											27
<i>Rhygoplitis</i> sp.	<i>Prunus serotina</i> (<i>Parornix</i> or <i>Phyllonorycter</i>)	Black Cherry	M		x									45
<i>Sathon</i> sp.	<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i> (<i>Caloptilia rhoifoliella</i>)	Poison Ivy	M	x										
<i>Stiropius</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Bucculatrix</i>)	Scrub Oak	co-coon											49
Alysiinae: Dacnusiini sp.	<i>Ilex verticillata</i> (<i>Phytomyza</i>)	Winterberry	M	x										
Alysiinae sp.	<i>Bidens connata</i> (<i>Calycomyza platyptera</i>)	Purple-stemmed Beggar-ticks	M,S											40
Alysiinae sp.	<i>Quercus velutina</i> (<i>Japanagromyza viridula</i>)	Black Oak	M	x										
Alysiinae sp.	<i>Woodwardia areolata</i> (<i>Chirosia</i> sp.)	Netted Chain Fern	M	x										
Braconinae sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Stilbosis</i>)	Scrub Oak	M,S	x										
Exothecinae/Hormiinae sp.	<i>Amelanchier</i> (<i>Parornix</i> sp.)	Shadbush	M, L											24

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Exothecinae/Hormiinae sp.	<i>Aronia arbutifolia</i> (<i>Parornix arbutifoliella</i>)	Red Chokeberry	M, L											24
Exothecinae/Hormiinae sp.	<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i> (<i>Parornix</i> n. sp.)	Maleberry	M,S											52
Exothecinae/Hormiinae sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> (<i>Caloptilia</i> sp.)	Highbush Blueberry	M,S	x										37
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Acer rubrum</i> (<i>Cameraria aceriella</i>)		M,S	x										
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Corylus cornuta</i> (<i>Cameraria corylisella</i>)	Beaked Hazelnut	M,S	x										
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i> (<i>Parornix</i> n. sp.)	Maleberry	M,S						x					
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Phragmites australis</i>	Common Reed	M,S											40
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Quercus stellata</i> (<i>Coptotriche</i>)	Post Oak	M,S											65
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Quercus velutina</i> (<i>Coptotriche castaneaeella</i>)	Black Oak	M,S	x										24
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Scirpus</i> (<i>Monochroa</i>)	Bulrush	M,S											61
Microgastrinae sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> (<i>Parornix preciosella</i>)	Highbush Blueberry	M,S											37
Miracinae sp.	<i>Corylus</i> (<i>Cameraria corylisella</i>)	Hazelnut	M,S											44
Opiinae sp.	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> (<i>Liriomyza</i>)	Groundsel	M,S			x								
Opiinae sp.	<i>Baptisia tinctoria</i> (<i>Liriomyza baptisiae</i>)	Wild Indigo	M,S											59
Opiinae sp.	<i>Cakile edentula</i> (<i>Liriomyza brassicae</i>)	Sea Rocket	M,S											50
Opiinae sp.	<i>Ilex verticillata</i> (<i>Phytomyza</i>)	Winterberry	M,S											4
Opiinae sp.	<i>Melampyrum lineare</i> (<i>Liriomyza</i>)	Cow-wheat	M,S											44
Opiinae sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Japanagromyza viridula</i>)	Scrub Oak	M,S											27
Opiinae sp.	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i> (<i>Cerodontha ?scirpivora</i>)	Woolly Bulrush	M,S											40

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Opiinae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Calycomyza solidaginis</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M,S											23, 27
Opiinae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Liriomyza</i> , <i>Nemorimyza</i> <i>posticata</i> , <i>Phytomyza</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M,S	x					x					
Braconidae sp.	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> (<i>Cerodontha ?incisa</i>)	Orchard Grass	M,S											31
Braconidae sp.	<i>Euthamia</i> (<i>Liriomyza</i>)	Grass-leaved Goldenrod	M,S						x					
Braconidae sp.	<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i> (<i>Coptodisca magnella</i>)	Huckleberry	M,S					x						
Braconidae sp.	<i>Gaylussacia frondosa</i> (<i>Coptodisca magnella</i>)	Dangleberry	M,S											31, 44
Braconidae sp.	<i>Quercus alba</i> (<i>Japanagromyza viridula</i>)	White Oak	M,S	x										
Braconidae sp.	<i>Rubus</i> (<i>Ectoedemia</i> <i>rubifoliella</i>)	Dewberry	M,S											61
Braconidae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Phytomyza</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M,S											45
Braconidae sp.	<i>Vitis labrusca</i> (<i>Antispila</i> sp.)	Fox Grape	M,S											32
Cynipidae (Gall Wasps)														
<i>Acraspis pezomachoides</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	G	x										
<i>Acraspis prinoides</i> (Beutenmüller 1892)	<i>Quercus prinoides</i>	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G											7, 8
<i>Amphibolips quercusilicifoliae</i> (Bassett, 1864)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G		x									27
<i>Amphibolips quercusjuglans</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G			x								31
<i>Amphibolips</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x										
<i>Amphibolips</i> sp.	<i>Quercus velutina</i>	Black Oak	G	x									x	
<i>Amphibolips</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G		x									7
<i>Andricus flavohirtus</i> Beutenmüller, 1913	<i>Quercus prinoides</i>	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G		x									55
<i>Andricus quercuspetiolicola</i> (Bassett, 1863)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. prinoides</i>	White Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G	x	x	x								
<i>Callirhytis balanacea</i> Weld, 1944	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x	x									

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<i>Callirhytis clavula</i> (Osten Sacken, 1865)	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	G			x								
<i>Callirhytis quercusoperator</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G	x										19
<i>Callirhytis quercuspunctata</i> (Bassett, 1863)	<i>Quercus velutina</i>	Black Oak	G			x							x	
<i>Callirhytis quercusscintula</i> (Bassett, 1864)	<i>Quercus velutina</i>	Black Oak	G	x										
<i>Callirhytis quercusventricosa</i> (Bassett, 1864)	<i>Quercus ×rehderii?</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x										57, 59
<i>Diastrophus</i> sp.	<i>Rubus flagellaris</i>	Northern Dewberry	G						x					
<i>Diplolepis bicolor</i> (Harris, 1841)	<i>Rosa</i>	Rose	G							x				1, 45
<i>Diplolepis rosaefolii</i> (Cockerell, 1889)	<i>Rosa rugosa</i> , <i>Rosa</i> sp.	Rose	G		x								x	47
<i>Diplolepis spinosa</i> (Ashmead, 1887)	<i>Rosa rugosa</i>	Rugosa Rose	G											2
<i>Diplolepis</i> sp.	<i>Rosa palustris</i>	Swamp Rose	G											49
<i>Disholcaspis quercusglobulus</i> (Fitch, 1859)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. prinoides</i>	White Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G	x	x	x								7, 28
<i>Dryocosmus albidus</i> Weld, 1944	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G		x									
<i>Dryocosmus deciduus</i> (Beutenmüller, 1913)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G											57
<i>Dryocosmus imbricariae</i> (Ashmead, 1896)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x										27, 73
<i>Dryocosmus quercuspalustris</i> (Osten Sacken, 1861)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G	x	x	x								19, 26, 44
<i>Melikaiella tumifica</i> (Osten Sacken, 1865)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G			x								24
<i>Neuroterus niger</i> Gillette, 1888	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	G										x	
<i>Neuroterus perminimus</i> Bassett, 1900	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	G	x										
<i>Neuroterus quercusbatatus</i> (Fitch, 1859)	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	G										x	
<i>Neuroterus quercusverrucarum</i> (Osten Sacken, 1861)	<i>Quercus prinoides</i>	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak												7
<i>Philonix nigra</i> (Gillette, 1889)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. prinoides</i>	White Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G,S		x	?							x	

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<i>Phylloteras poculum</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Quercus prinoides</i>	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G		x									8
<i>Synergus</i> sp.	<i>Quercus alba</i> (<i>Andricus quercuspetiolicola</i>), <i>Rosa rugosa</i> (<i>Diplolepis rosaefolii</i>)	White Oak, Beach Rose	G			x								47
<i>Zapatella davisae</i> Buffington & Melika, 2016	<i>Quercus velutina</i>	Black Oak	G	x										
<i>Zapatella quercusphellos</i> (Osten Sacken, 1861)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G	x	x								x	19
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G,S	x	x			x	x				x	31, 36, 57
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x										
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G		x									
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G		x									
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G											24
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G											57
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G	x	x			x	x					10, 27
<i>Cynipini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus prinoides</i>	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G		x									
<i>Synergini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G											24
<i>Synergini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus velutina</i> (<i>Callirhytis quercussimilis</i>)	Black Oak	G											19
<i>Synergini</i> sp.	<i>Quercus prinoides</i> (<i>Disholcaspis quercusglobulus</i>)	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G											28
Encyrtidae (Encyrtid Wasps)														
<i>Ageniaspis bicoloripes</i> (Girault, 1915)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Cameraria quercivorella</i> , <i>Phyllonorycter rileyella</i> , <i>Phyllonorycter</i> sp.)	Scrub Oak	M,S		x									39, 48
<i>Ageniaspis</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Cameraria quercivorella</i>), <i>Viburnum dentatum</i> (<i>Marmara viburnella</i>)	Scrub Oak, Arrowwood	M	x										19, 24, 60

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Encyrtidae sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Phyllonorycter</i> sp.)	Scrub Oak												27
Eulophidae (Eulophid Wasps)														
<i>Achrysocharoides</i> cf. <i>bisulcus</i> Yoshimoto, 1977 (n. sp.?)	<i>Lespedeza</i> (<i>Porphyrosela</i> <i>desmodiella</i>)	Bush Clover	M											48
<i>Achrysocharoides</i> sp.	<i>Corylus</i> (<i>Cameraria</i> <i>corylisella</i>)	Hazelnut	M,S											44
<i>Achrysocharoides</i> (n. sp.?)	<i>Morella pensylvanica</i> (<i>Cameraria picturatella</i>)	Bayberry	M, S		x									35
<i>Achrysocharoides</i> sp.	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i> (<i>Phyllonorycter viburnella</i>)	Arrowwood	M,S										x	48
<i>Aprostocetus</i> sp.	<i>Solidago</i> (dipteran rosette gall)	Goldenrod	G, S											4
<i>Chrysocharis assis</i> (Walker, 1839)	<i>Gaylussacia frondosa</i> (<i>Coptodisca magnella</i>)	Dangleberry	M,S											31
<i>Chrysocharis</i> cf. <i>nephereus</i> (Walker, 1839)	<i>Lonicera morrowii</i> (<i>Aulagromyza</i> <i>luteoscutellata</i>)	Morrow's Honeysuckle	M,S											23
<i>Chrysocharis occidentalis</i> (Girault, 1916)	<i>Morella pensylvanica</i> (<i>Cameraria picturatella</i>), <i>Smilax</i> (<i>Proleucoptera</i> <i>smilaciella</i>)	Bayberry, Greenbrier	M, S	x		x								57
<i>Chrysocharis prodice</i> (Walker, 1839)	<i>Prunus serotina</i> (<i>Coptodisca</i> <i>splendoriferella</i>)	Black Cherry	M, S										x	
<i>Chrysocharis pubicornis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> , <i>Tanacetum parthenium</i> (<i>Phytomyza syngenesiae</i>)	Oxeye Daisy, Feverfew	M,S											20
<i>Chrysocharis</i> sp.	<i>Ilex glabra</i> (<i>Phytomyza</i> <i>glabricola</i>)	Inkberry	M, S											20
<i>Chrysocharis</i> sp.	<i>Solidago odora</i> (<i>Calycomyza solidaginis</i>)	Sweet Goldenrod	M, S											32
<i>Closterocerus cinctipennis</i> Ashmead, 1888	<i>Ilex verticillata</i> (<i>Phytomyza</i>), <i>Lonicera</i> <i>morrowii</i> (<i>Aulagromyza</i> <i>luteoscutellata</i>)	Winterberry, Morrow's Honeysuckle	M,S											4, 23

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Closterocerus</i> nr. <i>damastes</i> Walker, 1847	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Stigmella</i>)	Scrub Oak	M, S		x									
<i>Closterocerus trifasciatus</i> Westwood, 1833	<i>Morella pensylvanica</i> (<i>Cameraria picturatella</i>), <i>Phragmites australis</i> (<i>Elachista</i> sp.), <i>Quercus</i> <i>ilicifolia</i> (<i>Brachys</i> sp., <i>Phyllonorycter</i> sp.)	Bayberry, Common Reed, Scrub Oak	M, S		x									24, 40, 57
<i>Closterocerus utahensis</i> Crawford, 1912	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Stigmella</i> sp.), <i>Vitis</i> <i>labrusca</i> (<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.)	Scrub Oak, Fox Grape	G, M, S											4, 57
<i>Closterocerus</i> sp.	<i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i> (<i>Mompha solomoni</i>)	Buttonbush	M											33
<i>Closterocerus</i> sp.	<i>Ilex verticillata</i> (<i>Phytomyza</i>)	Winterberry	M											35
<i>Closterocerus</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Stigmella nigriverticella</i>)	Scrub Oak	M,S											31
" <i>Closterocerus</i> " n. sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> (<i>Coptodisca</i> sp.)	Highbush Blueberry	M						x					
" <i>Closterocerus</i> " sp. (possibly undescribed species in a group that will be removed from <i>Closterocerus</i>)	<i>Vitis labrusca</i> (<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.)	Fox Grape	G, S											4
<i>Elasmus</i> sp.	<i>Desmodium ciliare</i> (<i>Porphyrosela</i> <i>desmodiella</i>)	Hairy Small-leaved Tick-trefoil	M,S											31
<i>Elasmus</i> sp.	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i> (<i>Phyllonorycter viburnella</i>)	Arrowwood	M, S											24
<i>Hemiptarsenus</i> sp.	<i>Schoenoplectus pungens</i> (<i>Cosmopterix scirpicola</i>)	Common Threesquare	M											56
<i>Horismenus fraternus</i> (Fitch, 1856)	<i>Quercus alba</i> (<i>Bucculatrix</i> <i>trifasciella</i>), <i>Q. ilicifolia</i> (<i>Cameraria quercivorella</i> , <i>Phyllonorycter rileyella</i>)	White Oak, Scrub Oak	M,S											39, 44

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Pediobius albipes</i> (Provancher, 1887)	<i>Carex swanii</i> (<i>Cerodontha ?morosa</i>), <i>Morella caroliniensis</i> (<i>Stigmella myricafoliella</i>)	Swan's Sedge, Bayberry	M,S	x										44
<i>Pediobius aphidiphagus</i> (Ashmead, 1887)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Amphibolips</i> sp.)	Scrub Oak	G, S		x									
<i>Pnigalio flavipes</i> (Ashmead, 1886)	<i>Anemone quinquefolia</i> (<i>Phytomyza multifidae</i>)	Wood Anemone	M, S											27
<i>Pnigalio pallipes</i> (Provancher, 1887)	<i>Anemone quinquefolia</i> (<i>Phytomyza multifidae</i>), <i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i> (<i>Mompha solomoni</i>), <i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> (<i>Phytomyza syngenesiae</i>)	Wood Anemone, Buttonbush, Oxeye Daisy	M, S											20, 27, 33
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Euthamia caroliniana</i> , <i>E. graminifolia</i> (<i>Liriomyza</i>)	Slender Goldenrod, Grass-leaved Goldenrod	M,S						x					
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Juncus tenuis</i> (<i>Cerodontha</i>)	Path Rush	M,S	x										
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Morella caroliniensis</i> (<i>Cameraria picturatella</i>)	Bayberry	M											44
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Phragmites australis</i> (<i>Elachista</i>)	Common Reed	M,S											40
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Brachys ovatus</i>)	Scrub Oak	M,S											65
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Cameraria quercivorella</i>)	Scrub Oak	M											48
<i>Pnigalio</i> spp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Eriocraniella platyptera</i>)	Scrub Oak	M, S											24
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Neurobathra strigifinitella</i>)	Scrub Oak	M											24
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Quercus stellata</i> (<i>Coptotriche</i>)	Post Oak	M,S											65
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Rubus</i> (<i>Metallus rohweri</i>)	Dewberry	M											53
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Liriomyza eupatorii</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M											23

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<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Triadenum virginicum</i> (<i>Fomoria hypericella</i>)	Marsh St. Johnswort	M,S											31
<i>Pnigalio</i> sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> (<i>Coptodisca</i> sp.)	Highbush Blueberry	M						x					
<i>Quadrastichus</i> sp.	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i> (<i>Marmara viburnella</i>)	Arrowwood	M, S											58
<i>Sympiesis argenticoxae</i> Girault, 1917	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> (<i>Caloptilia</i> sp.)	Highbush Blueberry	M	x										
<i>Sympiesis sericeicornis</i> (Nees, 1834)	<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i> (<i>Parornix</i> n. sp.), <i>Prunus serotina</i> (<i>Phyllonorycter</i>), <i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Coptotriche citrinipennella</i>)	Maleberry, Black Cherry, Scrub Oak	M, S						x			x		
<i>Sympiesis</i> sp.	<i>Quercus velutina</i> (<i>Acrocercops albinatella</i>)	Black Oak	M			x								
<i>Sympiesis</i> sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> (<i>Caloptilia</i> sp.)	Highbush Blueberry	M	x										
<i>Tetrastichus</i> sp.	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i> (<i>Marmara viburnella</i>)	Arrowwood	M, S											58
<i>Zagrammosoma multilineatum</i> (Ashmead, 1888)	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> (<i>Liriomyza</i>), <i>Lespedeza</i> (<i>Porphyrosela desmodiella</i>), <i>Rubus</i> (<i>Metallus</i>)	Groundsel, Bush Clover, Blackberry	M											32, 44, 48
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Aquilegia vulgaris</i> (<i>Phytomyza aquilegiana</i>)	Garden Columbine	M											23
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Arctium</i> (<i>Phytomyza syngenesiae</i>)	Burdock	M,S											68
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> (<i>Nemorimyza posticata</i>)	Groundsel	M,S			x								
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Baptisia tinctoria</i> (<i>Liriomyza baptisiae</i>)	Wild Indigo	M,S		x									
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Bolboschoenus robustus</i> (<i>Acalypttris</i>)	Sturdy Bulrush	M,S											44
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> (<i>Cerodontha ?incisa</i>)	Orchard Grass	M,S											31
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Glyceria septentrionalis</i> (<i>Cerodontha ?incisa</i>)	Eastern Manna Grass	M,S	x										

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Entedoninae sp.	<i>Lonicera morrowii</i> (<i>Aulagromyza</i>)	Morrow's Honeysuckle	M,S											18
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Prunus serotina</i> (<i>Gracillariidae</i> sp.)	Black Cherry	M,S											45
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Amphibolips</i>)	Scrub Oak	G, S											31
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Schoenoplectus americanus</i> (<i>Acalyptris</i>)	Chairmaker's Bulrush	M,S											44
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Calycomyza solidaginis</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M,S											41
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Ophiomyia carolinensis</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M,S											23
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Spartina patens</i> (<i>Elachista</i>)	Saltmeadow Cordgrass	M,S											74
Entedoninae sp.	<i>Symphyotrichum lanceolatum</i> (<i>Calycomyza promissa</i>)	Lance-leaved Aster	M,S											40
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Baptisia tinctoria</i> (<i>Liriomyza baptisiae</i>)	Wild Indigo	M,S		x									
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Calamagrostis</i> (<i>Agromyzidae</i>)	Bluejoint	M,S						x					
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Ilex verticillata</i> (<i>Phytomyza</i>)	Winterberry	M											24
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Lonicera morrowii</i> (<i>Paraphytomyza</i>)	Morrow's Honeysuckle	M											23
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Nyssa sylvatica</i> (<i>Ectoedemia nyssaefoliella</i>)		M,S											73
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Stilbosis</i>)	Scrub Oak	M											44
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Salix</i> (<i>Caloptilia stigmatella</i>)	Willow	M											56
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Scirpus cyperinus</i> (<i>Cerodontha ?scirpivora</i>)	Woolly Bulrush	M,S											40
Eulophinae sp.	<i>Solidago altissima</i> (<i>Phytomyzinae</i>)	Tall Goldenrod	M											4
Tetrastichinae sp.	<i>Quercus prinoides</i> (<i>Neuroterus floccosus</i>)	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G											7

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Tetrastichinae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (dipteran rosette gall)	Elliott's Goldenrod	G,S	x										
Tetrastichinae sp.	<i>Symphotrichum dumosum</i> (<i>Rhopalomyia</i>)	Bushy Aster	G,S											35
Eulophidae sp.	<i>Iris versicolor</i> (<i>Cerodontha [Dizygomyza]</i>)	Blue Flag	M											31
Eupelmidae (Eupelmid Wasps)														
<i>Brasema gemmarii</i> (Ashmead, 1886)	<i>Quercus prinoides</i> (unidentified leaf gall)	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G, S											21
<i>Eupelmus messene</i> Walker, 1839	<i>Rosa palustris</i> (<i>Diplolepis</i> sp.), <i>Rubus flagellaris</i> (<i>Diastrophus</i> sp.), <i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Calycomyza solidaginis</i>)	Swamp Rose, Northern Dewberry, Elliott's Goldenrod	G, M						x					23, 49
Eurytomidae (Eurytomid Wasps)														
<i>Eurytoma</i> sp.	<i>Salix purpurea</i> (<i>Euura</i> sp.)	Basket Willow	G,S											40
<i>Rileyia</i> sp.	<i>Solidago sempervirens</i> (<i>Asphondylia</i> n. sp.)	Seaside Goldenrod	G											17
<i>Sycophila</i> sp.	<i>Quercus alba</i> (<i>Philonix nigra?</i>)	White Oak	G			x								
<i>Sycophila</i> sp.	<i>Quercus prinoides</i> (unidentified leaf gall)	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G											21
Eurytomidae sp.	<i>Rosa palustris</i> (<i>Diplolepis</i> sp.)	Swamp Rose	G											49
Figitidae (Figitid Wasps)														
<i>Gronotoma</i> sp.	<i>Solidago altissima</i> , <i>S. latissimifolia</i> (<i>Liriomyza</i>)	Tall Goldenrod, Elliott's Goldenrod	M	x										4, 45
<i>Trybliographa</i> sp.	<i>Rumex crispus</i> (<i>Pegomya</i>)	Curly Dock	M	x										18
<i>Zaeucoila robusta</i> (Ashmead, 1894)	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> (<i>Nemorimyza posticata</i>), <i>Melampyrum lineare</i> (<i>Liriomyza pistilla</i>)	Groundsel, Cow-wheat	M											22, 44
Eucoilinae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Calycomyza solidaginis</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M											56

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Ichneumonidae (Ichneumon Wasps)														
<i>Diadegma</i> sp. (tentative ID; poor specimen)	<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i> (<i>Lyonetia latistrigella</i>)	Maleberry	M						x					
<i>Scambus</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Coptotriche citrinipennella</i>)	Scrub Oak	M						x					
Ephialtini sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> (<i>Caloptilia</i> sp.)	Highbush Blueberry	M, L											52
Campopleginae sp. (<i>Enytus</i> ?)	<i>Prunus maritima</i> (<i>Coleophora umbratica</i>)	Beach Plum	M											19
Ichneumonidae sp.	<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i> (<i>Brachys</i>)	Maleberry	M											73
Mymaridae (Fairyflies)														
<i>Ooctonus</i> sp.	<i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i> (<i>Tamalia coweni</i> ?)	Bearberry	G?											24
Ormyridae (Ormyrid Wasps)														
<i>Ormyrus</i> sp.	<i>Rosa palustris</i> (<i>Diplolepis</i> sp.), <i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Callirhytis quercusventricosa</i> , <i>Polystepha pilulae</i> ?), <i>Q. prinoides</i> (<i>Philonix nigra</i> ?), <i>Rosa</i> (<i>Diplolepis rosaefolii</i>)	Swamp Rose, Scrub Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G	x	x									49, 59
Platygastridae (Platygastrid Wasps)														
<i>Metaclisis floridana</i> (Ashmead, 1887)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (<i>Macrodiplosis niveipila</i>)	Scrub Oak	G,S											26
<i>Platygaster tephrosiae</i> Buhl & Eiseman, 2017	<i>Tephrosia virginiana</i> (<i>Lasiopteridi</i> sp.)	Goat's Rue	G,S											
<i>Platygaster vitisiellae</i> Buhl & Eiseman, 2016	<i>Vitis labrusca</i> (<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.)	Fox Grape	G,S											19
<i>Synopeas cf. pubescens</i> (Ashmead, 1893)	<i>Quercus velutina</i> (<i>Macrodiplosis niveipila</i>)	Black Oak	G,S											19
<i>Trichacis virginiensis</i> Ashmead, 1893	<i>Parthenocissus quinquefolia</i> (<i>Dasineura parthenocissi</i>)	Virginia Creeper	G,S	x										
Platygastrinae sp.	<i>Smilax</i> (<i>Meunieriella</i>)	Greenbrier	G,S	x										
Platygastrinae sp.	<i>Symphotrichum dumosum</i> (<i>Rhopalomyia</i>)	Bushy Aster	G,S											35

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Pteromalidae (Pteromalid Wasps)														
<i>Halticoptera</i> sp.	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i> (<i>Phytomyza plantaginis</i>)	English Plantain	M,S											4
<i>Hemadas nubilipennis</i> (Ashmead, 1887)	<i>Vaccinium</i>	Lowbush Blueberry	G,S	x										10
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Cornus amomum</i> (<i>Parallelodiplosis subtruncata</i>)	Silky Dogwood	G,S											76
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius</i> (<i>Neolasioptera</i> sp.)	Pilewort	G,S											73
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i> (Cecidomyiidae)	Huckleberry	G,S											31
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i> (<i>Cerodontha dorsalis</i>)	Reed Canary Grass	M,S											40
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Rosa palustris</i> (<i>Diplolepis</i> sp.)	Swamp Rose	G,S											49
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Salix purpurea</i> (<i>Euura</i> sp.)	Basket Willow	G,S											40
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (<i>Calycomyza solidaginis</i>)	Elliott's Goldenrod	M,S											23
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> (dipteran rosette gall)	Elliott's Goldenrod	G,S	x										
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Solidago rugosa</i> (<i>Rhopalomyia clarkei</i>)	Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	G,S											32
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Symphyotrichum dumosum</i> (<i>Rhopalomyia</i>)	Bushy Aster	G,S											35
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Symphyotrichum lateriflorum</i> (<i>Ophiomyia parda</i>)	Calico Aster	M,S	x										
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Tanacetum parthenium</i> (<i>Phytomyzinae</i> sp.)	Feverfew	M,S											20
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Tephrosia virginiana</i>	Goat's Rue	G,S											51
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Vitis labrusca</i> (<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.)	Fox Grape	G,S	x										19
Pteromalidae sp.	<i>Woodwardia areolata</i> (<i>Chirosia</i> sp.)	Netted Chain Fern	M,S	x										

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Tenthredinidae (Common Sawflies)														
<i>Eutomostethus luteiventris</i> (Klug, 1816)	<i>Juncus effusus</i>	Soft Rush	M, L											67
<i>Euura</i> sp.	<i>Salix purpurea</i>	Basket Willow	G, S											40
<i>Fenusa pumila</i> Leach, 1817	<i>Betula populifolia</i>	Gray Birch	M, S											53, 66
<i>Fenusa ulmi</i> Sundevall, 1847	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	American Elm	M											40
<i>Metallus lanceolatus</i> (Thomson, 1870)	<i>Geum canadense</i>	White Avens	M	x										
<i>Metallus rohweri</i> MacGillivray, 1909	<i>Rubus cuneifolius</i> , <i>R. flagellaris</i> , <i>R. allegheniensis</i>	Dewberry, Blackberry	M			x								4, 19, 53
<i>Pontania</i> sp.	<i>Salix</i> sp., <i>S. occidentalis</i>	Willow, Dwarf Prairie Willow	G							x				67
<i>Profenusa lucifex</i> (Ross, 1936)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M	x										31, 73
<i>Pseudodineura parva</i> (Norton, 1867)	<i>Anemone quinquefolia</i>	Wood Anemone	M	x		x								27, 44
Torymidae (Torymid Wasps)														
<i>Torymus tubicola</i> (Osten Sacken, 1870)	<i>Quercus (Amphibolips</i> sp.)	Black or Scrub Oak	G											
<i>Torymus</i> sp.	<i>Amelanchier laevis (Blaesodiplosis canadensis)</i>	Smooth Shadbush	G	x										
<i>Torymus</i> sp.	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius (Neolasioptera</i> sp.)	Pilewort	G											37, 73
Torymidae sp.	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	G			x								
Torymidae sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia (Callirhytis quercusventricosa)</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x										
LEPIDOPTERA														
Bedelliidae (Bedelliid Moths)														
<i>Bedellia somnulentella</i> (Zeller, 1847)	<i>Calystegia</i>	Bindweed	M											40
Bucculatricidae (Ribbed Cocoon-maker Moths)														
<i>Bucculatrix ivella</i> Busck, 1900	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i>	Groundsel	M,L			x								4, 25, 33
<i>Bucculatrix pomifoliella</i> Clemens, 1860	<i>Amelanchier laevis, Aronia melanocarpa</i>	Smooth Shadbush, Black Chokeberry	M									x		31
<i>Bucculatrix trifasciella</i> Clemens, 1866	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	S											19, 44

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Bucculatrix</i> sp.	<i>Corylus cornuta</i>	Beaked Hazelnut	M											31
<i>Bucculatrix</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	L											31, 49
Coleophoridae (Casebearer Moths)														
<i>Coleophora comptoniella</i> (McDunnough, 1926)	<i>Morella caroliniensis</i>	Bayberry	M											68
<i>Coleophora kalmiella</i> (McDunnough, 1936)	<i>Kalmia angustifolia</i>	Sheep Laurel	M											72
<i>Coleophora rosacella</i> Clemens, 1864	<i>Rosa</i>	Rose	M, S	x		x								
<i>Coleophora rupestrella</i> McDunnough, 1955	<i>Fragaria virginiana</i> , <i>Potentilla simplex</i>	Wild Strawberry, Common Cinquefoil	M, S	x	x									
<i>Coleophora umbratica</i> Braun, 1914	<i>Prunus maritima</i>	Beach Plum	M											19
<i>Coleophora</i> sp.	<i>Comptonia peregrina</i>	Sweetfern	M						x					
<i>Coleophora</i> sp.	<i>Ulmus</i>	Elm	M											13
Cosmopterigidae (Cosmet Moths)														
<i>Cosmopterix scirpicola</i> Hodges, 1962	<i>Schoenoplectus americanus</i> , <i>S. pungens</i>	Chairmaker's Bulrush, Common Threesquare	M											44, 56
<i>Stilbosis</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M	x										27, 31, 44
Depressariidae (Depressariid Moths)														
<i>Menesta melanella</i> Murtfeldt, 1890	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	L		x									
Elachistidae (Elachistid Moths)														
<i>Elachista</i> sp.	<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	Common Velvet Grass	M											56
<i>Elachista</i> sp.	<i>Phragmites americanus</i> , <i>Phragmites australis</i>	American Reed, Common Reed	M											40, 79, Sesac hacha Pond
<i>Elachista</i> sp.	<i>Spartina patens</i> , <i>S. pectinata</i>	Saltmeadow Cordgrass, Prairie Cordgrass	M											74
<i>Perittia herrichiella</i> (Herrich- Schäffer, 1855)	<i>Lonicera morrowii</i>	Morrow's Honeysuckle	M											18
Eriocraniidae (Eriocraniid Moths)														
<i>Eriocraniella platyptera</i> Davis, 1978	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M, S	x						x				19, 24, 27

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
Gelechiidae (Twirler Moths)														
<i>Chrysoesthia sexguttella</i> (Thunberg, 1794)	<i>Chenopodium</i>	Lambsquarters	M											14
<i>Dichomeris ligulella</i> Hübner, 1818	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (contaminant in <i>Dyseriocrania griseocapitella</i> vial)	Scrub Oak	(M)											27
<i>Exoteleia pinifoliella</i> (Chambers, 1880)	<i>Pinus rigida</i>	Pitch Pine	M											24, 45
<i>Filatima pseudacaciella</i> (Chambers, 1872)	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	Black Locust	L											3
<i>Gnorimoschema</i> sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	G	x										
<i>Keiferia inconspicuella</i> (Murtfeldt, 1883)	<i>Solanum carolinense</i>	Horsenettle	M											62
<i>Monochroa</i> sp.	<i>Scirpus</i>	Bulrush	M											61
<i>Scrobipalpa</i> nr. <i>atriplicella</i> (von Röslerstamm, 1839)	<i>Atriplex</i>	Orache	M,S											70
<i>Taygete sylvicolella</i> (Busck, 1903)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> (in <i>Callirhytis quercusventricosa</i> galls)	Scrub Oak	G, S	x										
Gracillariidae (Leaf Blotch Miner Moths)														
<i>Acrocercops albinatella</i> (Chambers, 1872)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	White Oak, Scrub Oak, Black Oak	M			x								49
<i>Callisto denticulella</i> (Thunberg, 1794)	<i>Malus</i>	Crabapple	M											40
<i>Caloptilia hypericella</i> (Braun, 1918)	<i>Hypericum adpressum</i>	Creeping St. Johnswort	L,S											66
<i>Caloptilia porphyretica</i> (Braun, 1923)	<i>Rhododendron</i>	Azalea	M, L	x										
<i>Caloptilia rhoifoliella</i> (Chambers, 1876)	<i>Rhus typhina</i> , <i>Toxicodendron radicans</i>	Staghorn Sumac, Poison Ivy	M, L	x		x							x	19, 23, 31
<i>Caloptilia sassafrasella</i> (Chambers, 1876)	<i>Sassafras albidum</i>	Sassafras	M,L, S	x										
<i>Caloptilia serotina</i> (Ely, 1910)	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry	M											24
<i>Caloptilia stigmatella</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	<i>Populus alba</i> , <i>P. tremuloides</i> , <i>Salix purpurea</i>	White Poplar, Quaking Aspen, Basket Willow	M, L											54, 56, 73
<i>Caloptilia</i> sp.	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red Maple	L	x										31
<i>Caloptilia</i> sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	Highbush Blueberry	M	x					x					52, 73

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Cameraria aceriella</i> (Clemens, 1859)	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red Maple	M	x										
<i>Cameraria cincinnatiella</i> (Chambers, 1871)	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	M										x	
<i>Cameraria corylisella</i> (Chambers, 1871)	<i>Corylus cornuta</i>	Beaked Hazelnut	M	x		x							x	31, 44
<i>Cameraria guttifinitella</i> (Clemens, 1859)	<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i>	Poison Ivy	M	x		x								23, 67
<i>Cameraria picturatella</i> (Braun, 1916)	<i>Morella caroliniensis</i>	Bayberry	M		x	x		x		x	x	x	x	23, 27,
<i>Cameraria quercivorella</i> (Chambers, 1879)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M											19, 39, 48
<i>Cameraria</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. alba</i>	Scrub Oak, White Oak	M	x	x			x	x				x	31, 57
<i>Chrysaster ostensackenella</i> (Fitch, 1859)	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	Black Locust	M											3
<i>Creastobombycia solidaginis</i> (Frey & Boll, 1878)	<i>Solidago gigantea</i> , <i>S. latissimifolia</i> , <i>S. rugosa</i>	Late Goldenrod, Elliott's Goldenrod, Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	M	x								x		23, 40, 41, 18
<i>Gracillaria syringella</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	<i>Ligustrum</i>	Privet	M, L											42
<i>Leucospilapteryx venustella</i> (Clemens, 1860)	<i>Mikania scandens</i>	Climbing Hempvine	M											79
<i>Marmara fasciella</i> (Chambers, 1875)	<i>Pinus strobus</i>	White Pine	M											24
<i>Marmara salictella</i> Clemens, 1863	<i>Salix purpurea</i>	Basket Willow	M											40
<i>Marmara serotinella</i> Busck, 1915	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry	M											24
<i>Marmara viburnella</i> Eiseman & Davis, 2017	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i>	Arrowwood	M,S	x		x	x		x			x	x	23, 24, 48, 58, 60
<i>Marmara</i> sp.	<i>Corylus americana</i>	American Hazelnut	M	x										
<i>Marmara</i> sp.	<i>Iva frutescens</i>	Marsh Elder	M											44
<i>Marmara</i> sp.	<i>Nyssa sylvatica</i>	Tupelo	M			x								
<i>Marmara</i> sp.	<i>Sisyrinchium fuscatum</i>	Sandplain Blue-eyed Grass	M,S											32
<i>Neurobathra strigifinitella</i> (Clemens, 1860)	<i>Castanea mollissima</i> , <i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. stellata</i>	Chinese Chestnut, Scrub Oak, Post Oak	M,S	x				x	x		x			24, 27, 49,

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Parectopa robiniella</i> Clemens, 1863	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	Black Locust	M											3
<i>Parornix geminatella</i> (Packard, 1869)	<i>Prunus maritima</i>	Beach Plum	M, L											19
<i>Parornix kalmiella</i> (Dietz, 1907)	<i>Kalmia angustifolia</i>	Sheep Laurel	M											49, 66
<i>Parornix peregrinaella</i> (Darlington, 1949)	<i>Comptonia peregrina</i>	Sweetfern	M, L											66
<i>Parornix preciosella</i> (Dietz, 1907)	<i>Vaccinium angustifolium</i> , <i>V. corymbosum</i>	Lowbush Blueberry, Highbush Blueberry	M	x										37, 51
<i>Parornix quadripunctella</i> (Clemens, 1861)	<i>Aronia arbutifolia</i> , <i>Aronia melanocarpa</i>	Red Chokeberry, Black Chokeberry	M, L									x		24
<i>Parornix</i> n. sp.	<i>Lyonia ligustrina</i>	Maleberry	M						x					31, 52
<i>Parornix</i> sp.	<i>Amelanchier nantucketensis</i> , <i>Amelanchier</i> sp.	Nantucket Shadbush, Shadbush	M, L											24, 51
<i>Parornix</i> sp.	<i>Betula populifolia</i>	Gray Birch	M, L											66
<i>Parornix</i> sp.	<i>Crataegus</i> sp., <i>Malus</i> sp.	Hawthorn, Apple	M											67
<i>Phyllocnistis ampelopsiella</i> Chambers, 1871	<i>Parthenocissus quinquefolia</i>	Virginia Creeper	M									x		27
<i>Phyllocnistis liriodendronella</i> Clemens, 1863	<i>Liriodendron tulipifera</i>	Tulip Tree	M											3, 73
<i>Phyllocnistis insignis</i> Frey & Boll, 1876	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius</i>	Pilewort	M											40
<i>Phyllocnistis vitegenella</i> Clemens, 1859	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	M	x		x								6, 27, 31, 32, 49
<i>Phyllonorycter aeriferella</i> (Clemens, 1859)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. ilicifolia</i>	White Oak, Scrub Oak	M	x	x				x				x	
<i>Phyllonorycter basistrigella</i> (Clemens, 1859)	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	M	x										
<i>Phyllonorycter diversella</i> (Braun, 1916)	<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i> , <i>G. frondosa</i>	Huckleberry, Dangleberry	M	x										31, 36
<i>Phyllonorycter intermixta</i> (Braun, 1930)	<i>Corylus americana</i> , <i>C. cornuta</i>	American Hazelnut, Beaked Hazelnut	M											24, 31
<i>Phyllonorycter propinquinella</i> (Braun, 1908)	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry	M, S											15, 45

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Phyllonorycter rileyella</i> (Chambers, 1875)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M					x						39
<i>Phyllonorycter viburnella</i> (Braun, 1923)	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i>	Arrowwood	M	x									x	24, 48
<i>Phyllonorycter</i> sp.	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red Maple	M											31
<i>Phyllonorycter</i> sp.	<i>Lonicera morrowii</i>	Morrow's Honeysuckle	M											19
<i>Porphyrosela desmodiella</i> (Clemens, 1859)	<i>Desmodium ciliare</i> , <i>Lespedeza</i>	Hairy Small-leaved Tick-trefoil, Bush Clover	M						x					31, 48
<i>Povolnya quercinigrella</i> (Ely, 1915)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. stellata</i>	White Oak, Scrub Oak, Post Oak	M											39, 44, 52, 64, 65
<i>Parornix</i> or <i>Phyllonorycter</i>	<i>Amelanchier</i> , <i>Prunus serotina</i>	Shadbush, Black Cherry	M	x	x							x	x	24, 32
<i>Parornix</i> or <i>Phyllonorycter</i>	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	Highbush Blueberry	M	x									x	
<i>Telamoptilia hibiscivora</i> D. & M. Davis, 2017	<i>Hibiscus moscheutos</i>	Swamp Rose-mallow	M											74
Ornixoninae n. gen., n. sp.	<i>Morella caroliniensis</i>	Bayberry	M											45
Heliozelidae (Shield-bearer Moths)														
<i>Antispila</i> cf. <i>isabella</i> Clemens, 1860	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	M	x		x							x	6, 23, 31, 32, 53, 80
<i>Antispila nysaefoliella</i> Clemens, 1860	<i>Nyssa sylvatica</i>	Tupelo	M	x		x								73
<i>Aspilanta ampelopsifoliella</i> (Chambers, 1874)	<i>Parthenocissus quinquefolia</i>	Virginia Creeper	M, S	x										31, 80
<i>Aspilanta argentifera</i> Braun, 1927	<i>Comptonia peregrina</i> , <i>Morella caroliniensis</i>	Sweetfern, Bayberry	M, S						x					57, 66
<i>Aspilanta oinophylla</i> (van Nieukerken & Wagner, 2012)	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	M											80
<i>Coptodisca kalmiella</i> Dietz, 1921	<i>Kalmia angustifolia</i>	Sheep Laurel	M, S											72
<i>Coptodisca lucifluella</i> (Clemens, 1860)	<i>Carya tomentosa</i>	Mockernut Hickory	M	x										31
<i>Coptodisca magnella</i> Braun, 1916	<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i> , <i>G. frondosa</i>	Huckleberry, Dangleberry	M					x	x		x	x		31, 36, 44, 51

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Coptodisca splendoriferella</i> (Clemens, 1860)	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry	M		x								x	15, 67
<i>Coptodisca</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M											31
<i>Coptodisca</i> sp.	<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>	Highbush Blueberry	M						x			x		31, 73
<i>Heliozela aesella</i> Chambers, 1877	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G	x										23, 32, 63
Incurvariidae (Leafcutter Moths)														
<i>Paraclemensia acerifoliella</i> (Fitch, 1854)	<i>Castanea mollissima</i> , <i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. stellata</i> , <i>Vaccinium angustifolium</i> , <i>V. corymbosum</i>	Chinese Chestnut, Scrub Oak, Post Oak, Lowbush Blueberry, Highbush Blueberry	L	x					x		x			49, 51, 64, 65, 73
Lyonetiidae (Lyonetiid Moths)														
<i>Lyonetia latistrigella</i> Walsingham, 1882	<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i> , <i>Lyonia ligustrina</i>	Huckleberry, Maleberry	M						x					24
<i>Proleucoptera smilaciella</i> (Busck, 1900)	<i>Smilax</i>	Greenbrier	M	x									x	31, 37
Momphidae (Momphid Moths)														
<i>Mompha solomoni</i> Wagner, Adamski & Brown, 2004	<i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i>	Buttonbush	M											33, 34, 38
<i>Mompha</i> n. sp.	<i>Crocantemum canadense</i>	Canada Frostweed	M, S				x							
Nepticulidae (Nepticulid Moths)														
<i>Acalyptis</i> sp.	<i>Bolboschoenus robustus</i> , <i>Schoenoplectus americanus</i> , <i>S. pungens</i>	Sturdy Bulrush, Chairmaker's Rush, Common Threesquare	M											44, 56, 81
<i>Ectoedemia heinrichi</i> Busck, 1914	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M		x									
<i>Ectoedemia nyssaefoliella</i> (Chambers, 1880)	<i>Nyssa sylvatica</i>	Tupelo	M	x										31, 73
<i>Ectoedemia quadrinotata</i> (Braun, 1917)	<i>Corylus cornuta</i>	Beaked Hazelnut	M											24, 31, 73
<i>Ectoedemia rubifoliella</i> (Clemens, 1860)	<i>Rubus</i>	Dewberry	M							x		x		61
<i>Ectoedemia virgulae</i> (Braun, 1927)	<i>Carya tomentosa</i> , <i>Corylus</i>	Mockernut Hickory, Hazelnut	M	x										31, 44
<i>Ectoedemia</i> n. sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M, S	x										31
<i>Fomoria hypericella</i> (Braun, 1925)	<i>Triadenum virginicum</i>	Marsh St. Johnswort	M											61
<i>Stigmella argentifasciella</i> (Braun, 1912)	<i>Tilia americana</i>	Basswood	M											19

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Stigmella caryaefoliella</i> (Clemens, 1861)	<i>Carya tomentosa</i>	Mockernut Hickory	M	x										
<i>Stigmella centifoliella</i> (Zeller, 1848)	<i>Rosa rugosa</i>	Rugosa Rose	M, S											47
<i>Stigmella corylifoliella</i> (Clemens, 1861)	<i>Corylus americana</i> , <i>C. cornuta</i> , <i>Gaylussacia baccata</i> , <i>Lyonia ligustrina</i> , <i>Rhododendron viscosum</i> , <i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i> , <i>V. macrocarpon</i>	American Hazelnut, Beaked Hazelnut, Huckleberry, Maleberry, Swamp Azalea, Cranberry	M	x	x	x		x	x		x	x	x	23, 31, 32, 35, 61
<i>Stigmella crataegifoliella</i> (Clemens, 1861)	<i>Crataegus</i> sp.	Hawthorn	M											67
<i>Stigmella intermedia</i> (Braun, 1917)	<i>Rhus glabra</i>	Smooth Sumac	M											4
<i>Stigmella myricafoliella</i> (Busck, 1900)	<i>Morella caroliniensis</i>	Bayberry	M, S											31, 68
<i>Stigmella nigriverticella</i> (Chambers, 1875)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. stellata</i>	Scrub Oak, Post Oak	M, S	x										31, 65
<i>Stigmella oxyacanthella</i> (Stainton, 1854)	<i>Malus</i> sp.	Apple	M											73
<i>Stigmella populetorum</i> (Frey & Boll, 1878)	<i>Populus alba</i> , <i>P. grandidentata</i>	White Poplar, Bigtooth Aspen	M											31, 55, 73
<i>Stigmella prunifoliella</i> (Clemens, 1861)	<i>Prunus maritima</i> , <i>Prunus serotina</i>	Beach Plum, Black Cherry	M	x						x		x		23, 32, 34
<i>Stigmella quercipulchella</i> (Chambers, 1882)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	M											73
<i>Stigmella rhoifoliella</i> (Braun, 1912)	<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i>	Poison Ivy	M	x		x								31
<i>Stigmella slingerlandella</i> (Kearfott, 1908)	<i>Prunus maritima</i> , <i>Prunus serotina</i>	Beach Plum, Black Cherry	M		x									9
<i>Stigmella villosella</i> (Clemens, 1861)	<i>Rubus</i> , <i>Rubus hispidus</i>	Blackberry, Bristly Dewberry	M			x			x	x				31
<i>Stigmella</i> sp.	<i>Aronia melanocarpa</i>	Black Chokeberry	M										x	
<i>Stigmella</i> sp.	<i>Betula populifolia</i>	Gray Birch	M											66
<i>Stigmella</i> sp.	<i>Morella caroliniensis</i>	Bayberry	M							x		x		
<i>Stigmella</i> sp.	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. prinoides</i> , <i>Q. rubra</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	White Oak, Scrub Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak, Red Oak, Black Oak	M	x	x	x					x		x	31, 57

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Stigmella</i> sp.	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Rose	M						x					20
Tischeriidae (Tischeriid Moths)														
<i>Coptotriche aenea</i> (Frey & Boll, 1873)	<i>Rubus flagellaris</i> , <i>R. hispidus</i>	Northern Dewberry, Bristly Dewberry	M,S		x	x				x		x		39
<i>Coptotriche castaneaeella</i> (Chambers, 1875)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	White Oak, Scrub Oak, Black Oak	M	x	?				x					24, 31, 49, 73
<i>Coptotriche citrinipennella</i> (Clemens, 1859)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	M	x	x				x				x	24, 39, 64
<i>Coptotriche fuscomarginella</i> (Chambers, 1875)	<i>Quercus alba</i> ?, <i>Q. ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. prinoides</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	White Oak?, Scrub Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak, Black Oak	M	x	?	x							?	39
<i>Coptotriche purinosella</i> (Chambers, 1875)	<i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. stellata</i>	White Oak, Post Oak	M,S	x										31, 44, 52, 65
<i>Coptotriche</i> sp.	<i>Aronia arbutifolia</i>	Red Chokeberry	M											24
<i>Tischeria quercitella</i> Clemens, 1863	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	M		x	x			x					31, 73
Tortricidae (Tortricid Moths)														
<i>Catastega aceriella</i> Clemens, 1861	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red Maple	L	x										
<i>Catastega timidella</i> Clemens, 1861	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. prinoides</i>	Scrub Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	L		x			x						55
<i>Epiblema otiosana</i> (Clemens, 1860)	<i>Bidens</i>	Beggar-ticks	G											39
<i>Gynnidomorpha romonana</i> (Kearfott, 1907)	<i>Limonium carolinianum</i>	Sea Lavender	M											44
<i>Rhopobota</i> sp.	<i>Ilex verticillata</i>	Winterberry	M			x							x	
DIPTERA														
Agromyzidae (Leafminer Flies)														
<i>Agromyza aristata</i> Malloch, 1915	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	American Elm	M											78
<i>Agromyza ?idaeiana</i> Hardy, 1853	<i>Potentilla simplex</i> , <i>Rosa</i> sp., <i>R. multiflora</i>	Common Cinquefoil, Rose, Multiflora Rose	M	x										4, 18, 23, 24, 45, 67, 71
<i>Agromyza vockerothi</i> Spencer, 1969	<i>Rubus allegheniensis</i>	Blackberry	M			x								18

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Agromyza</i> sp.	<i>Dichantheium</i>	Rosette-panicgrass	M	x										31
<i>Agromyza</i> sp.	<i>Populus alba</i>	White Poplar	M											73
<i>Amauromyza flavifrons</i> (Meigen, 1830)	<i>Saponaria officinalis</i>	Bouncing Bet	M											2,12
<i>Amauromyza pleuralis</i> Malloch, 1914	<i>Catalpa</i>	Catalpa	M											77
<i>Aulagromyza cornigera</i> (Griffiths, 1973)	<i>Lonicera japonica</i>	Japanese Honeysuckle	M				x							
<i>Aulagromyza luteoscutellata</i> (de Meijere, 1924)	<i>Lonicera morrowii</i>	Morrow's Honeysuckle	M, S											4, 14, 18, 19, 23, 41
<i>Aulagromyza populicola</i> (Walker, 1853)	<i>Populus grandidentata</i>	Bigtooth Aspen												31
<i>Calycomyza menthae</i> Spencer, 1969	<i>Mentha spicata</i>	Spearmint	M											40
<i>Calycomyza platyptera</i> (Thomson, 1869)	<i>Bidens connata</i> , <i>Iva frutescens</i>	Purple-stemmed Beggar-ticks, Marsh Elder	M											40, 44
<i>Calycomyza promissa</i> (Frick, 1956)	<i>Symphotrichum lanceolatum</i>	Lance-leaved Aster	M											31, 40
<i>Calycomyza solidaginis</i> (Kaltenbach, 1869)	<i>Solidago altissima</i> , <i>S. latissimifolia</i> , <i>S. odora</i> , <i>S. sempervirens</i>	Late Goldenrod, Elliott's Goldenrod, Sweet Goldenrod, Seaside Goldenrod	M, S	x		x						x	x	16, 19, 23, 32, 41, 56
<i>Calycomyza</i> sp.	<i>Euthamia graminifolia</i>	Grass-leaved Goldenrod	M											27
<i>Cerodontha (Butomomyza) angulata</i> (Loew, 1869)	<i>Carex crinita</i> , <i>Dichantheium clandestinum</i> , <i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Fringed Sedge, Deertongue Grass, Path Rush	M	x										31, 63, 73
<i>Cerodontha (Cerodontha) dorsalis</i> (Loew, 1863)	<i>Glyceria septentrionalis</i> , <i>Phalaris arundinacea</i>	Eastern Manna Grass, Reed Canary Grass	M	x										40
<i>Cerodontha (Dizygomyza) edithae</i> Eiseman & Lonsdale, 2018	<i>Iris versicolor</i>	Blue Flag	M, S											31
<i>Cerodontha (Dizygomyza) cf. morosa</i> (Meigen, 1839)	<i>Carex swanii</i>	Swan's Sedge	M	x										
<i>Cerodontha (Dizygomyza) cf. scirpivora</i> Spencer, 1969	<i>Scirpus</i>	Bulrush	M											31, 40

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Cerodontha (Dizygomyza) thompsoni</i> (Frick, 1952)	<i>Iris versicolor</i>	Blue Flag	M											40, 61
<i>Cerodontha (Poemyza) cf. incisa</i> (Meigen, 1830)	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> , <i>Glyceria septentrionalis</i> , <i>Juncus tenuis</i>	Orchard Grass, Eastern Manna Grass, Path Rush	M	x										31
<i>Cerodontha</i> sp.	<i>Carex lurida</i>	Lurid Sedge	M											27
<i>Japanagromyza viridula</i> (Coquillett, 1902)	<i>Castanea mollissima</i> , <i>Quercus alba</i> , <i>Q. ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. prinoides</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Chinese Chestnut, White Oak, Scrub Oak, Dwarf Chinquapin Oak, Black Oak	L, M, S	x	x		x							19, 24, 27, 44, 73
<i>Liriomyza asclepiadis</i> Spencer, 1969	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	Common Milkweed	M											11, 20
<i>Liriomyza baptisiae</i> (Frost, 1931)	<i>Baptisia tinctoria</i>	Wild Indigo	M		x				x	x				59
<i>Liriomyza blechi</i> Spencer, 1973	<i>Plantago major</i>	Common Plantain	M											31
<i>Liriomyza brassicae</i> (Riley, 1884)	<i>Cakile edentula</i>	Sea Rocket	M											50
<i>Liriomyza carphophori</i> Eiseman, Lonsdale & Feldman, 2019	<i>Mikania scandens</i>	Climbing Hempvine	M											79
<i>Liriomyza eupatorii</i> (Kaltenbach, 1873)	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> , <i>Solidago altissima</i> , <i>S. latissimifolia</i> , <i>Symphotrichum lanceolatum</i> , <i>S. lateriflorum</i>	Groundsel, Tall Goldenrod, Elliott's Goldenrod, Lance- leaved Aster, Calico Aster	M, S	x		x								4, 18, 23, 27, 31, 40, 44
<i>Liriomyza fricki</i> Spencer, 1965	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover												75
<i>Liriomyza orillensis</i> Spencer, 1969	<i>Nabalus trifoliolatus</i>	Three-leaved Rattlesnake-root	M	x										
<i>Liriomyza pistilla</i> Lonsdale, 2017	<i>Melampyrum lineare</i>	Cow-wheat	M		x									44
<i>Liriomyza</i> sp.	<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	Sweet Vernal Grass	M				x							
<i>Liriomyza</i> sp.	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius</i>	Pilewort	M											74
<i>Liriomyza</i> sp.	<i>Euthamia graminifolia</i>	Grass-leaved Goldenrod	M						x					
<i>Liriomyza</i> sp.	<i>Pseudognaphalium obtusifolium</i>	Sweet Everlasting	M											73
<i>Nemorimyza maculosa</i> (Malloch, 1913)	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius</i> , <i>Erigeron canadensis</i> ,	Pilewort, Horseweed	M, S											12, 20, 25, 33, 40, 43, 73, 74

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Nemorimyza posticata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i> , <i>Solidago altissima</i> , <i>S. latissimifolia</i> , <i>Teucrium canadense</i>	Groundsel, Tall Goldenrod, Elliott's Goldenrod, American Germander	M, S	x		x	x							4, 19, 22, 23, 44, 76
<i>Ophiomyia carolinensis</i> Spencer, 1986	<i>Symphyotrichum lateriflorum</i>	Calico Aster	M	x										
<i>Ophiomyia congregata</i> (Malloch, 1913)	<i>Nabalus trifoliolatus</i>	Three-leaved Rattlesnake-root	M	x										
<i>Ophiomyia kwansonis</i> Sasakawa, 1961	<i>Hemerocallis</i>	Daylily	M											20
<i>Ophiomyia maura</i> (Meigen, 1838)	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	M, S	x										23, 45
<i>Ophiomyia parda</i> Eiseman & Lonsdale, 2018	<i>Symphyotrichum lateriflorum</i>	Calico Aster	M	x										
<i>Ophiomyia</i> sp.	<i>Euthamia caroliniana</i> , <i>E. graminifolia</i>	Slender Goldenrod, Grass-leaved Goldenrod	M									x		27, 31, 73
<i>Ophiomyia</i> sp.	<i>Nabalus trifoliolatus</i>	Three-leaved Rattlesnake-root	M											31
<i>Ophiomyia</i> sp.	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	Common Dandelion	M											20
<i>Phytoliriomyza clara</i> (Melander, 1913)	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	Bracken Fern	M			x								
<i>Phytoliriomyza melampyga</i> (Loew, 1869)	<i>Impatiens capensis</i>	Jewelweed	M	x										18, 40
<i>Phytomyza aquilegiana</i> Frost, 1930	<i>Aquilegia vulgaris</i>	Garden Columbine	M											23
<i>Phytomyza aquilegivora</i> Spencer, 1969	<i>Aquilegia vulgaris</i>	Garden Columbine	M											23
<i>Phytomyza astotinensis</i> Griffiths, 1976	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	M	x										
<i>Phytomyza crassiseta</i> Zetterstedt, 1860	<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i>	Germander Speedwell	M											Burnell St.
<i>Phytomyza glabricola</i> Kulp, 1968	<i>Ilex glabra</i>	Inkberry	M											20
<i>Phytomyza ilicicola</i> Loew, 1872	<i>Ilex opaca</i>	American Holly	M											19, 31
<i>Phytomyza ilicis</i> species group	<i>Ilex verticillata</i>	Winterberry	M	x		x								4, 35
<i>Phytomyza multifidae</i> Sehgal, 1971	<i>Anemone quinquefolia</i>	Wood Anemone	M, S											27
<i>Phytomyza plantaginis</i> Robineau-desvoidy, 1851	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	English Plantain	M											4

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Phytomyza ranunculi</i> (Schrank, 1803)	<i>Ranunculus</i>	Buttercup	M, S											20, 40
<i>Phytomyza spondylii</i> Robineau-desvoidy, 1851	<i>Heracleum maximum</i>	Cow Parsnip	M, S											30
<i>Phytomyza syngenesiae</i> (Hardy, 1849)	<i>Arctium</i> , <i>Bidens</i> , <i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> , <i>Sonchus asper</i> , <i>Tanacetum parthenium</i>	Burdock, Beggar-ticks, Oxeye Daisy, Spiny Sowthistle, Feverfew	M, S											1, 18, 20, 62, 68
<i>Phytomyza wiggii</i> Lonsdale & Scheffer, 2011	<i>Ilex verticillata</i>	Winterberry	M											24
<i>Phytomyza</i> sp.	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius</i>	Pilewort	M											37
<i>Phytomyza</i> sp.	<i>Erigeron</i>	Fleabane	M											20
<i>Phytomyza</i> sp.	<i>Eurybia divaricata</i>	White Wood Aster	M	x										
<i>Phytomyza</i> sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	M											23
Phytomyzinae sp.	<i>Euthamia caroliniana</i> , <i>Euthamia graminifolia</i> var. <i>graminifolia</i>	Slender Goldenrod, Grass- leaved Goldenrod	M	x										37
Agromyzidae sp. (long, narrow)	<i>Baccharis halimifolia</i>	Groundsel	M			x								
Agromyzidae sp.	<i>Calamagrostis</i>	Reed Grass	M						x					
Agromyzidae sp.	<i>Hieracium</i>	Hawkweed	M											24
Anthomyiidae (Root-maggot Flies)														
<i>Chirosia filicis</i> (Huckett, 1949)	<i>Osmundastrum cinnamomeum</i>	Cinnamon Fern	M, S	x										
<i>Chirosia gleniensis</i> (Huckett, 1924)	<i>Woodwardia areolata</i>	Netted Chain Fern	M	x										
<i>Pegomya rufescens</i> (Stein, 1898)	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Purslane	M											23
<i>Pegomya</i> sp.	<i>Rumex acetosella</i> , <i>R. crispus</i> , <i>R. obtusifolius</i>	Sheep Sorrel, Curly Dock, Bitter Dock	M	x										12, 18, 41
Cecidomyiidae (Gall Midges)														
<i>Acericecis ocellaris</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Acer rubrum</i>	Red Maple	G	x										31
<i>Asphondylia rosulata</i> Dorchin, 2015	<i>Solidago rugosa</i>	Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	G											41
<i>Asphondylia</i> sp.	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	G	x										
<i>Asphondylia</i> sp.	<i>Solidago sempervirens</i>	Seaside Goldenrod	G,S											17
<i>Asteromyia carbonifera</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> , <i>S. rugosa</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod, Rough- stemmed Goldenrod	G	x	x			x						3

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Asteromyia euthamiae</i> Gagné, 1968	<i>Euthamia caroliniana</i> , <i>E. graminifolia</i> var. <i>graminifolia</i>	Slender Goldenrod, Grass-leaved Goldenrod	G		x				x	x	x			31, 33, 73
<i>Asteromyia modesta</i> (Felt, 1907)	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	G											23
<i>Asteromyia</i> sp.	<i>Symphotrichum dumosum</i>	Bushy Aster	G,S											35
<i>Blaesodiplosis canadensis</i> (Felt, 1908)	<i>Amelanchier</i>	Shadbush	G	x										31
<i>Caryomyia tubicola</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Carya tomentosa</i>	Mockernut Hickory	G											31
" <i>Cecidomyia</i> " <i>squamulicola</i> Stebbins, 1909	<i>Corylus</i>	Hazelnut	G										x	
<i>Contarinia cerasiserotinae</i> (Osten Sacken, 1871)	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry	G	x			x							
<i>Contarinia</i> sp.	<i>Gaylussacia frondosa</i>	Dangleberry	G	x										
<i>Contarinia</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G		x									36, 57
<i>Contarinia</i> sp.	<i>Rosa</i>	Rose	G											71
<i>Contarinia</i> sp.	<i>Sassafras albidum</i>	Sassafras	G	x		x								
<i>Contarinia</i> or <i>Dasineura</i>	<i>Corylus cornuta</i>	Beaked Hazelnut	G	x		x								
<i>Dasineura parthenocissi</i> (Stebbins, 1909)	<i>Parthenocissus quinquefolia</i>	Virginia Creeper	G	x										
<i>Dasineura smilacifolia</i> (Felt, 1911)	<i>Smilax</i>	Greenbrier	G										x	69
<i>Dasineura trifolii</i> Loew, 1874	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	White Clover	G											37
<i>Dasineura</i> sp.	<i>Ionactis linariifolius</i>	Flax-leaved Aster	G											59
<i>Dasineura</i> sp.?	<i>Lespedeza</i>	Bush Clover	G							x				
<i>Gliaspilota glutinosa</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Carya tomentosa</i>	Mockernut Hickory	G											31
<i>Lasioptera vitis</i> Osten Sacken, 1862	<i>Vitis labrusca</i> (<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.)	Fox Grape	G											19
<i>Lestodiplosis</i> sp.	<i>Juncus canadensis</i> (<i>Livia bifasciata</i>)	Canada Rush	G						x					
<i>Macrodiplosis erubescens</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G											24, 27, 36
<i>Macrodiplosis majalis</i> (Osten Sacken, 1878)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G		x									
<i>Macrodiplosis niveipela</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G	x	x	x								19, 26, 27
<i>Macrodiplosis qoruca</i> (Felt, 1925)	<i>Quercus alba</i>	White Oak	G			x								

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Macrodiplosis</i> sp.	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x										
<i>Meunieriella</i> sp.	<i>Smilax</i>	Greenbrier	G	x		x							x	27
<i>Monarthropalpus flavus</i> (Schrank, 1776)	<i>Buxus</i>	Boxwood	G											20
<i>Neolasioptera convolvuli</i> (Felt, 1907)	<i>Calystegia</i>	Bindweed	G											40
<i>Neolasioptera lycopi</i> (Felt, 1907)	<i>Lycopus uniflorus</i>	Northern Bugleweed	G											bamboo forest
<i>Neolasioptera nodulosa</i> (Beutenmüller, 1907)	<i>Rubus</i>	Blackberry	G			x								
<i>Neolasioptera perfoliata</i> (Felt, 1907)	<i>Mikania scandens</i>	Climbing Hempvine	G											79
<i>Neolasioptera potentillaecaulis</i> (Stebbins, 1909)	<i>Potentilla canadensis</i>	Dwarf Cinquefoil	G											59
<i>Neolasioptera</i> sp.	<i>Erechtites hieraciifolius</i>	Pilewort	G											37, 73
<i>Neolasioptera</i> sp.	<i>Iva frutescens</i>	Marsh Elder	G											44
<i>Parallelodiplosis subtruncata</i> (Felt, 1907)	<i>Cornus amomum</i>	Silky Dogwood	G											76
<i>Polystepha globosa</i> (Felt, 1909)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i>	Scrub Oak	G	x										
<i>Polystepha pilulae</i> (Beutenmüller, 1892)	<i>Quercus ilicifolia</i> , <i>Q. velutina</i>	Scrub Oak, Black Oak	G	x	x	x			x				x	27, 57
<i>Rabdophaga</i> sp.	<i>Salix purpurea</i>	Basket Willow	G											40
<i>Resseliella clavula</i> (Beutenmüller, 1892)	<i>Cornus florida</i>	Flowering Dogwood	G											63
<i>Resseliella liriodendri</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Liriodendron tulipifera</i>	Tulip Tree	G											3, 73
<i>Rhopalomyia clarkei</i> Felt, 1907	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i> , <i>S. rugosa</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod, Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	G	x										32
<i>Rhopalomyia fusiformae</i> Felt, 1907	<i>Euthamia caroliniana</i> , <i>E. graminifolia</i> var. <i>graminifolia</i>	Slender Goldenrod, Grass-leaved Goldenrod	G		x									73
<i>Rhopalomyia lobata</i> Felt, 1908	<i>Euthamia graminifolia</i> var. <i>graminifolia</i>	Grass-leaved Goldenrod	G											37
<i>Rhopalomyia</i> sp.	<i>Symphotrichum dumosum</i>	Bushy Aster	G											35
<i>Rhopalomyia</i> sp.?	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	G	x										
<i>Sackenomyia commota</i> Gagné, 1975	<i>Viburnum dentatum</i>	Arrowwood	G	x		x							x	23

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Species	Host plant (host insect)	Host plant common name	Sign	SQ	MA	CO	LF	LL	PP	SH	SP	TS	TU	GPS
<i>Schizomyia viticola</i> (Osten Sacken, 1862)	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G			x								
<i>Trotteria</i> sp.	<i>Solidago rugosa</i> (<i>Asphondylia</i> sp.)	Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	G, S											41
<i>Vitisiella brevicauda</i> Felt, 1908	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G			x								4, 40, 63
<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G	x										
<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G	x		x								6, 40
<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G			x								6
<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G										x	
<i>Vitisiella</i> sp.	<i>Vitis labrusca</i>	Fox Grape	G, S										x	19
Lasiopteridi sp.	<i>Tephrosia virginiana</i>	Goat's Rue	G, S							x				51
Cecidomyiidae sp.	<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i>	Huckleberry	G											31
Cecidomyiidae sp.	<i>Quercus prinoides</i>	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G											59
Cecidomyiidae sp.	<i>Salix purpurea</i>	Basket Willow	G											40
Cecidomyiidae sp.?	<i>Euthamia caroliniana</i>	Slender Goldenrod	G											73
Cecidomyiidae sp.?	<i>Solidago latissimifolia</i>	Elliott's Goldenrod	G	x										
Cecidomyiidae sp.?	<i>Solidago rugosa</i>	Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	G											41
Chloropidae (Frit Flies)														
<i>Elachiptera</i> sp.	<i>Bidens</i>	Beggar-ticks	(G), S											39
Phoridae (Scuttle Flies)														
<i>Megaselia nantucketensis</i> Eiseman & Hartop, 2015	<i>Quercus velutina</i> (<i>Macrodiplosis niveipila</i>)	Black Oak												19
Tephritidae (Fruit Flies)														
<i>Procecidochares</i> sp.	<i>Solidago rugosa</i>	Rough-stemmed Goldenrod	G											18
NOT IDENTIFIED TO ORDER / FAMILY														
unidentified moth	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	Arborvitae	M											31
unidentified insect	<i>Bidens connata</i>	Purple-stemmed Beggar-ticks	M											40
unidentified insect	<i>Quercus prinoides</i>	Dwarf Chinquapin Oak	G											21
unidentified insect	<i>Salix occidentalis</i>	Dwarf Prairie Willow	G							x				
unidentified organism	<i>Bidens</i>	Beggar-ticks	G											39
unidentified organism	<i>Corylus cornuta</i>	Beaked Hazelnut	G	x										
unidentified organism	<i>Hydrocotyle</i>	Water Pennywort	G											81

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FUNGI														
<i>Dibotryon morbosum</i> (Schwein.) Theiss. & Syd., 1915	<i>Prunus serotina</i>	Black Cherry	G									x		
<i>Exobasidium vaccinii</i> (Fuckel) Woronin, 1867	<i>Gaylussacia baccata</i> , <i>G. frondosa</i> , <i>Rhododendron</i>	Huckleberry, Dangleberry, Azalea	G	x										44
<i>Gymnosporangium juniperi-virginianae</i> Schwein., 1822	<i>Juniperus virginiana</i>	Red Cedar	G											19
<i>Taphrina caerulescens</i> (Desm. & Mont.) Tul., 1866	<i>Quercus velutina</i> , <i>Q. alba</i>	Black Oak, White Oak	G	x									x	

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